

INTERFACE OPTIMISATION OF RECYCLED CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES

J. Howarth*, F.R. Jones, S.A. Hayes

¹ Department of Materials Science and Engineering, The University of Sheffield, Sheffield, UK.

* (mtp08jh@shef.ac.uk)

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1 Introduction

In the current climate, as the demand for more renewable resources increases, technologies have been developed to recycle carbon fibre from end of life composite [1], so as it may be re-used in other applications. The demand for these materials is driven by a greater social awareness of environmental issues. The composites industry wishes to exploit this and, potentially, appease national government and international unions in meeting “green” targets.

1.1 Recycling and Re-Working

Early techniques focused on simply burning off the resin. Although effective due to the vastly differing phase change properties of fibre and resin, this rather crude method often lead to damage done to the fibres left behind, as well as leaving the fibre surfaces inconsistently coated with impurities. Pioneered by research at the University of Nottingham, other techniques have been developed, such as dissolving the resin using a supercritical fluid [2]. These methods have the advantage of leaving behind less residue on the fibre surface and, synergistic with the environmental focus of recycling, are more energy efficient.

The next step is to convert the recycled fibre into a workable, usable material. Technical Fibre Products (TFP) of Cumbria, manufacture veils of recycled carbon fibre using a method akin to paper making. The final material is collected on a roll. Depending on the requirements, the fibre packing fraction of the sheet (i.e. its density) can be varied using this method.

The material used in this project has a basis weight of 10g^m-² (see Fig 1). These veils are very thin compared to e.g. chopped strand fibreglass or woven carbon fibre. This is deliberately so, as it is possible to achieve a higher packing density with a

thinner veil. Due to the nature of the manufacturing process, a thicker (higher basis weight) veil will have a lower density.

Fig 1: Optical micrograph of a section of the sheet

1.2 Aims

The main objective of the project is to manufacture composite materials from this recycled carbon fibre in order to assess their potential as industrial materials. The secondary objective is to enhance the materials’ mechanical properties by optimisation of the interface region. This region is essential to a composites’ ability to bear load, chemical treatments of the fibre surface have been applied to enhance this, facilitating the load transfer between matrix and fibre.

1.3 Plasma Treatment

A plasma is a partially or fully ionized gas, sometimes referred to as the fourth state of matter [3]. Plasma processes have a wide variety of applications in industry, though their use as

promoting adhesion in composite interfaces is relatively new.

Plasma treatment has been shown to improve the mechanical properties of carbon fibre composites previously [4]. These techniques are important, as carbon fibre surfaces are chemically inert; it is difficult to obtain a strong bond at the interface of fibre and matrix.

2 Experimental

Ten sheets of the carbon fibre veil of size 300 mm x 300 mm were cut and stacked together unidirectionally. This panel was then vacuum bagged and heated at 80°C for one hour to make a 100 gcm⁻² 'pre-form'.

From this panel were cut strips of size 160 mm x 70 mm (at 0°, 45° and 90° to the machine direction of the veil) so they fit into the plasma reactor chamber. Each end was taped to a petri dish so that the fibre sat centrally in the chamber.

Plasma treatment was carried out at low power A and high power B, and at treatment times of *x* mins (shortest), *y* mins and *z* mins (longest) to assess the effect of varying power and treatment time. Untreated controls were also cut and laid up for comparison.

Wet lay-up was the technique used for the composite manufacture. Two of the ten layer pre-forms were stacked together to form each unidirectional panel. An epoxy-based resin system was used for the matrix. The panels were cured in an envelope vacuum bag system at temperature(s) specified by the resin manufacturer.

Once cured, each panel was cut into tensile test strips of dimensions 100 mm x 5 mm. Fibreglass/polyester composite end tabs measuring 15 mm x 15 mm were affixed and the samples were tested in tension. Measured variables were tensile strength, Young's modulus and strain to failure.

3 Results and Discussion

Plasma treatment at power B for *z* mins improved tensile strength and Young's modulus (at all test angles [see Figs 2 and 3].)

N.B. In all graphs error bars depict one standard deviation plus and minus of the mean.

Fig 2: Comparing tensile strength of untreated samples to those treated at power B for *z* mins

Fig 3: Comparing Young's modulus of untreated samples to those treated at power B for *z* mins

The graphs indicate an improvement in the mechanical properties of the material. As the tests at 0° are largely dominated by the fibres and the tests at 90° by the matrix, a more detailed analysis was done for the tests at 45° to better show the effects of the interface on material properties.

When testing at 45° to the fibre alignment, we see a general increase in tensile strength as the plasma treatment becomes more aggressive (see Fig 4). It is also clear that the plasma power plays a more important role in determining material properties than treatment time.

Fig 4: Tensile strength of untreated and treated samples tested at 45°

However the difference in Young's modulus is very subtle (see Fig 5). There is an increase in all treated samples compared to the untreated control, however the values fall within the expected scatter. This is not surprising as Young's modulus is much more controlled by the fibres themselves rather than the interface region.

The treatment has also had little (if any) effect on strain (see Fig 6). This is due to the brittle nature of the material which is exacerbated by the composite being made with short fibre.

Fig 5: Young's modulus of untreated and treated samples tested at 45°

Fig 6: Strain to failure of untreated and treated samples tested at 45°

Further work will focus on treatments at higher plasma power. This way we will eventually over-treat the fibre and start to see a decrease in tensile strength. This will help us to establish the optimum treatment conditions for enhancing tensile strength.

4 Conclusions

Through plasma treatment we have an established method of enhancing the mechanical properties (particularly tensile strength) of our recycled carbon fibre composite.

It has been shown that the greatest effects are generally where plasma power is highest and treatment time is longest, although further work will be carried out to establish an optimum power/treatment time combination.

Generally it was shown that the treatments also improved Young's modulus and strain to failure, although there was no discernable difference in properties across plasma power and treatment time.

5 References

- [1] S. J. Pickering "Recycling technologies for thermoset composite materials – current status". *Composites Part A*, Vol. 37, pp 1206-1215, 2006.
- [2] J. R. Hyde, E. Lester, S. Kingman, S. Pickering, H. K. Wong "Supercritical propanol – a possible route to composite carbon fibre recovery: A viability study". *Composites Part A*, Vol. 37, pp 2171-2175, 2006.
- [3] Y. Eliezer and S. Eliezer "*The Fourth State of Matter: An Introduction to the Physics of Plasma*". Adam Hilger, 1989.

- [4] T. C. Chan "Plasma Surface Treatment in Composites Manufacturing". *Journal of Industrial Technology*, Vol. 15(1), Nov '98-Jan '99.